

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Technological Forecasting & Social Change

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/techfore

Boosting the EU forest-based bioeconomy: Market, climate, and employment impacts

Ragnar Jonsson^{a,*}, Francesca Rinaldi^a, Roberto Pilli^a, Giulia Fiorese^a, Elias Hurmekoski^b,
Noemi Cazzaniga^a, Nicolas Robert^a, Andrea Camia^a

^a European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Sustainable Resources, Bioeconomy Unit, Via E. Fermi 2749, Ispra, I-21027, Italy

^b Department of Forest Sciences, University of Helsinki, Latokartanonkaari 7, Helsinki 00790, Finland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Scenario analysis
Forest sector modelling
Bioeconomy
Sustainability
Employment
Climate change mitigation

ABSTRACT

This study adds to the scientific literature dealing with the climate change mitigation implications of wood substitution. Its main scientific contribution rests with the modelling approach. By fully integrating forest resource and wood-product markets modelling in quantitative scenario analysis, we account for international trade in wood products as well as impacts on EU forests and forest-based sector employment of an increased EU uptake of wood-based construction and/or biochemicals and biofuels. Our results confirm the crucial role of the sawmilling industry in the forest-based bioeconomy. Thus, boosting wood-based construction in the EU would be most effective in increasing EU production and employment—in logging and solid wood-products manufacturing, but also in sectors using sawmilling byproducts as feedstock. Vertical integration in wood-based biorefineries should thus be advantageous. The positive EU climate-change mitigation effects of increased carbon storage in harvested wood products (HWP) and material substitution from increased wood construction are more than offset by reduced net forests carbon sinks by 2030, due to increased EU harvests. Further, increased EU imports, resulting in lower consumption of sawnwood outside the EU, would reduce extra-EU long-life HWP carbon storage and substitution of GHG-intensive materials, highlighting the need for concerted international climate change mitigation.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The bioeconomy—as addressed in the 2018 update of the European Union (EU) Bioeconomy Strategy (European Commission, 2018)—covers all primary production sectors and all economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources and processes to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy, and services. The strategy, in aiming to create a sustainable, circular bioeconomy, is built around five main objectives—ensuring food and nutrition security; managing natural resources sustainably; reducing dependence on non-renewable resources for energy; mitigating and adapting to climate change; and strengthening European competitiveness and creating new jobs (Ibid.)—in supporting the EU's long-term vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate-neutral economy by 2050.

The forest-based industry is in many ways the perfect embodiment of

the circular bioeconomy, with side streams—wood chips, sawdust, and bark—from sawmills being used in the pulp & paper industry, in the production of wood-based panels, and for energy. Paper as well as solid wood products are recovered after having been used, serving as raw materials in production or for energy generation. The forest-based sector also plays an important role within the European bioeconomy. In 2015, forestry, manufacture of paper and wood products, and the furniture industry, together employed 2.6 million persons in the EU, compared with total employment in the EU bioeconomy of 13.5 million persons (Ronzon and M'barek, 2018). Further, forests and wood products can actively contribute to achieving the long-term goals set out in the Paris Agreement (Valade et al., 2017). The mitigation impact of the forest-based sector includes the amount of carbon directly removed by forests—on average about 400 million tons CO₂ per year during the period 2000 to 2015 (i.e., about 10% of total current EU GHG emissions), the mitigation potential provided by carbon sequestration in harvested wood products (HWP)—about 45 million tons CO₂ during the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: ragnar.jonsson@ec.europa.eu (R. Jonsson), roberto.pilli@ec.europa.eu (R. Pilli), giulia.fiorese@ec.europa.eu (G. Fiorese), elias.hurmekoski@helsinki.fi (E. Hurmekoski), noemi.cazzaniga@ext.ec.europa.eu (N. Cazzaniga), nicolas.robert@ec.europa.eu (N. Robert), andrea.camia@ec.europa.eu (A. Camia).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120478>

Received 4 June 2019; Received in revised form 11 November 2020; Accepted 12 November 2020

Available online 29 November 2020

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same period (United Nations Climate Change, 2018), and potential substitution benefits realized by using wood products in place of GHG-intensive materials and energy sources.

Construction (Antikainen et al., 2017; Hildebrandt et al., 2017; Toppinen et al., 2018) and biochemicals and biofuels (see, e.g., Natrass et al., 2016; European Commission, 2017) are considered to be amongst the most promising emerging wood-based product markets. Hence, the move towards performance-based common standards for Europe (EU, 2011), the introduction of engineered wood products (EWP), and pre-fabrication have boosted the competitiveness of wood in large-scale construction projects (Hurmekoski et al., 2015; Hildebrandt et al., 2017). Further, leading consumer brands such as P&G, IKEA, and the Coca-Cola Company have all set specific targets for replacing fossil-based chemicals or composites based on food crops with renewable and sustainable alternatives (Biddu et al., 2016). The demand for advanced biofuels is chiefly driven by policy (Hurmekoski et al., 2018). Thus the revised EU renewable energy directive promotes the transition from first generation biofuels to advanced biofuels, amongst the latter notably those produced from residues and wastes from forest-based industries (Council of the European Union, 2018).

Given their relevance, we intend to explore the implications of an increased uptake of wood-based construction, biochemicals and biofuels in terms of some of the objectives of the bioeconomy strategy, particularly as regards creating new jobs and mitigating climate change, in view of the potential synergies and trade-offs between said objectives.

1.2. Context

1.2.1. Futures studies

As the future does not yet exist, hypotheses regarding the future cannot be validated at present. However, as noted by Glenn (1999), the likelihood of a future event or condition can be changed by policy, and policy consequences can be forecast. The value of future-orientated research therefore lies not only in forecasting, but also in exploring alternative futures and their implications, as well as how to achieve desired outcomes (Bell, 2003).

Futures studies encompass a wide range of approaches and methods that can be classified in many ways, such as into those based on evidence vs. creativity and expertise vs. interaction (Popper, 2008). The applicability of the different approaches varies depending on the aim and scope of the study, not least the time horizon and the complexity of the studied system, i.e., the associated balance between predetermined processes and uncertainties.

In addition to projections of continued trends, it is the possible deviations from those trends that are of value for strategic planning. In simulation modelling—a quantitative tool for thinking—mathematical relationships are used to imitate a system; these relationships are then built into an internally consistent set of algorithms used mainly for forecasting environmental impacts (Duinker and Baskerville, 1986). Simulation models are frequently used for mid-range time horizons, when there is still considerable predictability about the future, but also considerable uncertainty (Kaivo-oja, 2001). This is why simulation modelling is most useful when applied in the context of scenario analysis. A key aim of scenario building is to extend thinking in terms of length of time—beyond five to ten years into the future—and breadth—across a range of possible futures (Duinker and Greig, 2007). Scenario analysis is most useful when uncertainties start to dominate over predetermined processes (Postma and Liebl, 2005). In this study, we apply simulation modelling to examine the implications of an expanding bioeconomy through policy-relevant scenarios.

The main contribution of the paper lies with the empirical application of simulation modelling in the context of an expanding bioeconomy, by integrating the analysis of the diffusion of new bioeconomy products and impact assessment for market interactions, climate change mitigation and employment. The paper takes a step towards a more dynamic modelling approach compared to earlier efforts (e.g., Eriksson et al.,

2012), and complements previous qualitative foresight literature (e.g., Pätäri et al., 2016; Purkus et al., 2018) on the expected and possible changes in the forest-based bioeconomy sector and its cascade impacts. Compared to earlier foresight approaches on this topic, it brings evidence-based results to support more concrete strategic planning and vision building.

1.2.2. Framework for modelling the forest-based bioeconomy

The main contribution of this study lies in the empirical approach for addressing substitution in the forest products markets both in terms of market developments and net GHG emissions. This study further contributes to addressing the issue of integrating the impact of new wood-based products into the forest sector, which is not possible with conventional econometric approaches due to the lack of data with sufficiently long time series.

Market developments determine the environmental impacts of the sector. Forest-based sector activities can mitigate climate change through two main mechanisms: by storing carbon in forests or wood products and by substituting wood for more greenhouse gas-intensive energy sources or materials (see, e.g., Gustavsson et al., 2006; Eriksson et al., 2007; Eriksson et al., 2012; Valade et al., 2017). Enhancing wood-based substitution through increased wood harvests can, however, conflict with the use of forests for carbon sequestration (Ibid.). Separate studies of either forests or wood products might thus lead to conflicting policy recommendations, due to potential trade-offs between sequestration and substitution options (Pingoud et al., 2010). The estimated effective mitigation potential in integrated studies depends greatly on how substitution coefficients are defined and which wood-use value chains and fossil-fuel based reference system are considered (Valade et al., 2017). Study results range from reduced (see, e.g., Perez-Garcia et al., 2007; Lundmark et al., 2014) to increased (see, e.g., Hudiburg et al., 2011; Kallio et al., 2013) atmospheric CO₂ concentrations over time. Several integrated studies analyse the CO₂ emission implications of substituting wood for other construction materials (e.g., Gustavsson et al., 2006; Upton et al., 2007; Pingoud et al., 2010; Eriksson et al., 2012), on different scales ranging from building components (Pingoud et al., 2010), to entire buildings (Gustavsson et al., 2006), to national (Upton et al., 2007) and international (Eriksson et al., 2012) level. Of these substitution studies, only Eriksson et al. (2012) assess the implications of increased wood-based construction on international wood-product markets, registering increased net imports in the EU/EFTA region. However, Eriksson et al. (2012) only model carbon impacts using a Swedish forest model, i.e., without considering European-level impacts. In addition, there is no feedback from the forest model to the global wood-product markets model. None of these integrated studies address the employment implications. However, if increased wood substitution should lead to increased domestic harvests and production of wood-based products, it would then create jobs in the forest-based sector (see Karttunen et al., 2018 and Kallio et al., 2018).

A plethora of studies—mostly analysing the impacts of increased energy use of wood (e.g., Lauri et al., 2012; Moiseyev et al., 2014; Forsell et al., 2016; Frank et al., 2016; Johnston and van Kooten, 2016; Jonsson and Rinaldi, 2017; Jonsson et al., 2018)—has demonstrated that increased use of wood-based commodities in one region can have significant impact not only on harvest and production in that region, but also on harvest, production and consumption in other regions through inter-regional trade. This means that the carbon flow results of increased wood substitution in one region is affected by international trade in wood products.

The forest industry is characterized by feedback loops and interconnections between its different parts (Johnston and van Kooten, 2016; Jonsson and Rinaldi, 2017; Hurmekoski et al., 2018). By- and co-products from sawmilling are used in the manufacture of wood-based panels, pulp & paper, and wood pellets, while wood-based chemicals and energy processes are largely produced from side and waste streams of chemical pulp production (see, e.g., Hurmekoski et al., 2018). Hence,

Fig. 1. Industry module of the GFTM.

market prospects for wood construction influence the availability of raw material for several downstream wood-based industries competing for these feedstocks, at the same time as the demand for these downstream products are synergic with sawnwood production; increased demand for and ensuing higher prices of byproducts and residues lowers the cost of production of the main product (see, e.g., Johnston and van Kooten, 2016; Jonsson et al., 2017). Further, forest resource development, not least the short-term forest sink, is largely driven by roundwood harvests, while in turn wood-using sectors rely on forests for raw materials (Jonsson et al., 2018). This means that the joint analysis of forest resources and wood-product markets, fully accounting for interdependencies and international trade, is a prerequisite for quantifying the potential of the forest-based sector to mitigate climate change (Ibid.), while also accounting for the employment impacts of increased consumption of wood-based products.

Accordingly, we aim to contribute to the scientific literature dealing with the climate change mitigation implications of wood substitution by widening the scope of study, accounting for international trade in wood products as well as the impacts on EU forests and forest-based sector employment of an increased EU uptake of wood-based construction and/or biochemicals and biofuels. In particular, we fully explore potential future synergies and trade-offs between different uses of forest-based resources in terms of climate change mitigation and employment. To achieve this aim, we integrate a forest resource model with a global wood-product markets model, and, performing specific analyses of carbon substitution effects and forest-based sector employment, assess how different substitution approaches fare in terms of roundwood harvests, production and trade of wood products, carbon stock changes, and forest sector employment. The focus of the study is the EU, but future global wood-product markets implications are assessed.

Next, the modelling approaches and data used are presented. Thereafter the scenario analysis setup is described, followed by presentation and discussion of modelling results. The paper concludes with methodological, policy and managerial implications.

2. Methods and data

This paper builds on modelling outcomes of the Global Forest Trade Model (GFTM), integrated with the forest Carbon Budget Model (CBM), as well as specific analysis of carbon substitution effects and forest-based sector employment. Next follows a description of the modelling and data sets used.

2.1. Wood-product markets

GFTM (for further details, see Jonsson et al., 2016; Jonsson and Rinaldi, 2017, 2018) is an economic equilibrium model for the forest-based sector, deriving projections for the consumption, production and international trade of wood-based products under different scenarios. GFTM covers 48 countries and sub-regions of the world. GFTM shares with other similar models a theoretical formulation based on spatial equilibrium theory in competitive markets for several commodities (Samuelson, 1952).

GFTM is based on the maximization of the welfare of the whole forest sector (consumer, primary/industrial products-producers and traders), subject to feasibility, resources, productivity, and equilibrium constraints. The model is static in that, given the number of projection periods, the optimal welfare is computed at each iteration with imperfect foresight. GFTM provides projections of: (i) consumption, production and net trade levels for final products; (ii) harvested, industrially processed and net traded quantities for primary products, and (iii) produced and traded quantities for intermediate products.

The supply/availability of local products is determined in the transformation process. Fig. 1 depicts the transformation process, simulated in GFTM by means of the industry module. The input-output representation through industry matrices is convenient, since it allows us to account for interrelationships amongst the various products. Pulpwood is depicted both as a primary and as an intermediate product because wood chips and particles resulting from sawmilling and plywood production (intermediate pulpwood) have the same uses as (primary) pulpwood.

Maximum potential supply of coniferous and non-coniferous roundwood (henceforth MWS)—further divided into sawlogs and pulpwood based on FAOSTAT production data series (FAOSTAT, 2017)—are ingested by GFTM as upper bounds for the provision of coniferous and non-coniferous sawlogs and pulpwood respectively, used in the transformation process in each country. As for the cost of roundwood supply, the slope of cost curves depends solely on the price elasticity of the timber supply. For the starting period, the timber supply shift parameter is derived from actual data for sawlogs and pulpwood removals and prices of sawlogs and pulpwood. The supply shifter is then updated from period to period, based on growing stock development. Inputs regarding MWS and growing stocks are compiled from various sources, as detailed in Jonsson et al. (2018). For EU member states, data are retrieved from the CBM (see Appendix B).

2.2. Carbon dynamics

The forest C dynamic is estimated for 26 EU countries (EU-28 excluding Malta and Cyprus) using the CBM model (Kurze et al., 2009), considering as main inputs age class distribution, volume, and increment data reported by national forest inventories and forest management plans. By adding the effect of harvests and natural disturbances (fire, wind storms, etc.), the model estimates, for the historical period 2000–2015, the evolution of living biomass, dead organic matter (DOM), and soil, under specific management conditions, defined at country level. All the main methodological premises are based on the assumptions reported in Pilli et al. (2016a), updated with the most recent input data. The strong correlation between the total C stock change estimated by CBM (Y) and the amount of harvest (X), verified both at country and at EU level, allowed us to derive a simple linear model ($Y = a + bX$) to infer the short-term evolution of the forest C stock change at EU level, under different harvest scenarios (see Appendix A for details). The total GHG removals were finally calibrated ex-post, to match the historical emissions and removals reported by MSs, in the 2018 GHG inventories (IPCC, 2014). The demand for industrial roundwood (IRW), as estimated by GFTM according to the MWS provided by CBM (see Appendix B), is used as activity data to estimate the HWP mitigation potential, using the IPCC Tier 2 approach (IPCC, 2014, also described in Pilli et al., 2015) and the potential material and energy substitution effect. In doing so, GFTM output as to net-trade is divided into imports and exports by applying shares from historical data series of FAOSTAT Production and Trade data. This last amount is estimated by multiplying the potential amount of wood used to substitute for other energy-intensive materials by a substitution factor (SF), assessing the amount of GHG emissions avoided by using wood products instead of other materials (see Table 6 and Appendix C for specific methodological details).

Annual harvests for fuelwood (FW) are estimated by combining information on past management practices (specifically defined at country level, within the CBM framework) and future levels of IRW harvest, as derived with GFTM (Jonsson et al., 2018). Specifically, we assume that the proportion between IRW and FW for the past remains constant in the future. Past levels of IRW and FW harvests (up to 2015) have been derived from FAOSTAT, and eventually corrected to harmonize the data across MSs (Pilli et al., 2015).

2.3. Employment

Data on employment in hours worked by sector (nama_10_a64_e in Eurostat, 2018) are crosschecked and complemented with data from national accounts (naio_10_cp16 in Eurostat, 2018) to derive as complete as possible a dataset on employment in forestry and logging, the woodworking industry, and manufacture of paper and paper products by country over the period 2009–2015. Dividing the reported time by sector production (source: CBM in the forestry sector, FAOSTAT production in the industrial sectors), labour productivity (in hours of work per quantity of wood-based goods produced by sector and country) is estimated.

Projections of employment are subsequently derived by dividing projections of roundwood removals and forest industry production by these labour productivity values. For the outlook period considered, i.e., until 2030, we assume unchanged labour productivity. Given possible continued productivity increases (Blombäck et al., 2003), resulting employment estimates give only the upper bound for employment changes.

3. Scenario assumptions

While the biophysical patterns underlying forest resource modelling—at least in the medium term—are predetermined to a considerable degree, market developments are fraught with considerable uncertainty (Jonsson et al., 2018). We are not attempting to make

Table 1

End-use shares. Translated from Merivuori (2009).

	Coniferous sawnwood	Coniferouslyplywood	Non- coniferous plywood	Particle board
Construction	49%	42%	40%	27%
Packaging	19%	25%		2%
Joinery and carpentry	14%			
Gardening & outdoor	6%			
Furniture	3%	4%	10%	71%
Other	9%		20%	
Mouldling		26%		
Transport		3%	30%	
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

predictions about future developments, but instead—applying simulation modelling—set out to assess the patterns of impact of a strong market uptake of wood-based construction and/or biochemicals and biofuels, discussing potential trade-offs and synergies between different objectives and the ensuing uses of forest-based resources.

In order to capture and analyse potential interconnections as fully as possible, this study encompasses four scenarios: Scenario I, a business-as-usual (BaU) scenario, where no major deviations from current market developments are foreseen; Scenario II, a scenario seeing increased wood-based construction; Scenario III, where the demand for biochemicals and biofuels increases; Scenario IV, combining scenarios II and III. In Scenario I, the BaU, harvests of industrial roundwood (within the bounds of non-decreasing growing stocks within forests available for wood supply), and the supply and demand of all processed wood-based products are derived by GFTM as solutions to the welfare-optimization problem under resource, technology and equilibrium constraints, without the addition of any further exogenous assumptions. Scenarios II and III are identical to BaU, with the exception of assuming a strong growth within the EU in demand for wood-based construction or biofuels and biochemicals respectively. This is assumed to result respectively in an increased demand for solid wood-based products in Scenario II, or chemical pulp by-products and residues in Scenario III. Scenario IV combines an increased demand for solid wood-based products and chemical pulp by-products and residues.

As regards future demand for solid wood-based products in scenarios II and IV, we draw on the high wood construction share scenario of Hildebrandt et al. (2017), foreseeing an increase in the wood construction quota (related to total area of residential floor space) in the EU from 4.9% in 2015 to 14% by 2030, and total residential floor space of new residential flooring of some 200 million m² by 2030. Composite future annual average growth rates for EU consumption of coniferous sawnwood (accounting also for EWP use of sawnwood) and wood-based panels are calculated as weighted averages of: (i) the growth rates in Hildebrandt et al. (2017) for use in construction and (ii) the average growth rates of the last five years leading up to 2015 for non-construction uses, applying the shares of different end-uses of Merivuori (2009) – see Table 1. Thus, for coniferous sawnwood and particle board, including orientated Strand board (OSB), we foresee total EU consumption of 128 million m³ (42% higher than in 2015) and 41 million m³ (15% higher than in 2015) respectively by 2030 in scenarios II and IV.

Wood-based chemicals and biofuels are not explicitly modelled in GFTM, due to a lack of data on production (volumes produced as well as input/output coefficients), consumption (and consequently also trade), and prices. The scarcity of data necessitates the approximation of the impacts of growing demand for wood-based chemicals and biofuels. Further, within the time frame of this study, 2030, the forest-based industry is expected to continue to rely chiefly on traditional pulp & paper value chains, as a result of long investment cycles, while a large-scale diffusion of novel wood-based chemicals and biofuels is highly

unlikely (Hurmekoski et al., 2018). Hence, for the purpose of scenarios III and IV, we assume that increased value-added production from side and waste streams of chemical pulp production—e.g., the use of lignin in polymer composites (see, e.g., Doherty et al., 2011; Schorr et al., 2014; Kun and Pukánszky, 2017), as a natural adhesive (Johnson and Hart, 2016), as concrete admixture (see, e.g., Hurmekoski et al., 2018)), and crude tall oil (CTO) used for biodiesel production (CTO based biodiesel is considerably more competitive than the thermochemical route (Pöyry, 2017)) besides its use in the pine chemical industry (Hurmekoski et al., 2018)—will result in increased prices for these by-products and residues.

We further assume—given rather limited trade of by-products—that these price increases are restricted to EU member states. Given the relatively abundant (potential) supply of lignin from chemical pulping (see, e.g., Kun and Pukánszky, 2017; Hurmekoski et al., 2018), we foresee real prices of lignin at the most 50% higher by 2030 than in 2015, i.e., an average annual increase of 2.74% of the original price of €209 per ton (drawing on Laurichesse and Avérous 2014). As for CTO, given that the supply is quite constrained (see, e.g., Peters and

Stojcheva, 2017; Hurmekoski et al., 2018), we expect that increased use of CTO for biodiesel production as well as different pine chemicals could result in a doubling of the starting price of €450 per ton (which draws on Peters and Stojcheva, 2017) by 2030, i.e., an average annual increase of 4.73%. Increased prices of byproducts and residues lowers the cost of production of the main product (see, e.g., Johnston and van Kooten, 2016; Jonsson et al., 2017). Thus, in the modelling, price increases of the byproducts lignin and crude tall oil result in decreased chemical pulp manufacturing costs proportionate to the output per ton of pulp (for details, see Hurmekoski et al., 2018, supplementary material).

The HWP mitigation potential is based on the amount of IRW attributed to each scenario. Within scenarios I—the BaU—and III, we assume that only the amount of fuelwood removed in 2030 provides a mitigation effect. The additional mitigation potential, compared with BaU, is given by the relative difference between scenario I and scenarios II and IV, on the amount of wood used for sawnwood (long-lived commodity, estimated by GFTM), for wood-based panels (medium-lived commodities, estimated by GFTM), and for fuelwood (as estimated in our study).

Table 2

EU production, consumption and net trade (sawnwood, plywood, particle board & OSB, and fibreboard: million m³ under bark; newsprint, printing & writing paper, packaging paper, household & sanitary paper, chemical pulp, and wood pellets: million metric tons).

BaU	Production			Consumption			Net trade		
	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030
Conif. sawnwood	96.9	98.8	100.9	91.0	91.5	92.5	6.0	7.3	8.4
Non-conif. sawnwood	11.2	11.5	11.9	11.2	11.3	11.5	0.0	0.2	0.4
Plywood	4.9	4.8	4.8	7.9	7.8	7.8	-3.0	-3.0	-3.0
particle board and osb	36.9	37.7	38.7	35.8	36.2	36.8	1.1	1.6	1.9
fibreboard	17.1	17.3	17.5	16.4	16.4	16.4	0.7	0.9	1.1
Newsprint	5.5	5.2	4.9	6.1	5.9	5.8	-0.6	-0.7	-0.8
Printing & writing	29.3	29.5	29.8	23.8	24.0	24.2	5.5	5.6	5.6
Packaging	46.6	45.2	44.7	44.2	42.7	41.9	2.3	2.6	2.8
Household & sanitary	7.5	7.7	8.1	7.7	7.9	8.3	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2
Chemical pulp	26.1	27.1	28.8	31.7	31.5	31.6	-5.6	-4.3	-2.8
Wood pellets	14.4	14.8	15.3	23.5	24.7	26.0	-9.2	-9.9	-10.6
Differences between Scenario II and the BaU scenario									
Conif. sawnwood	7.6	12.4	18.3	13.0	23.5	36.2	-5.4	-11.1	-17.9
Non-conif. sawnwood	-0.1	0.1	0.4	-0.1	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.2
Plywood	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
particle board and osb	1.5	3.6	5.2	1.5	3.5	4.6	0.0	0.0	0.7
fibreboard	-0.1	0.5	0.6	-0.1	0.5	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.1
Newsprint	0.0	0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
Printing & writing	-0.2	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.4	0.4	0.0	-0.2	-0.3
Packaging	-0.2	1.8	0.6	-0.3	2.0	0.6	0.1	-0.3	0.0
Household & sanitary	-0.1	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	-0.4	-0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0
Chemical pulp	-0.5	-0.6	0.4	-0.2	0.4	0.1	-0.3	-1.0	0.3
Wood pellets	0.1	0.2	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	0.1	0.2	-0.4
Differences between Scenario III and the BaU scenario									
Conif. sawnwood	0.1	-0.1	-2.1	0.1	0.0	-1.0	0.0	-0.1	-1.1
Non-conif. sawnwood	0.0	0.0	-0.4	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.2
Plywood	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
particle board and osb	0.0	0.0	-1.0	0.0	0.0	-0.6	0.0	0.0	-0.4
fibreboard	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.2
Newsprint	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.1
Printing & writing	0.1	0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.1	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
Packaging	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.7	0.0	0.0	-0.3
Household & sanitary	0.0	0.0	-0.4	0.0	0.0	-0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
Chemical pulp	0.1	0.1	-1.6	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-1.5
Wood pellets	0.0	0.0	-0.6	0.0	0.0	-1.3	0.0	0.1	0.7
Differences between Scenario IV and the BaU scenario									
Conif. sawnwood	7.8	12.4	18.3	13.0	23.5	35.8	-5.2	-11.1	-17.5
Non-conif. sawnwood	-0.2	0.0	0.4	-0.4	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.2
Plywood	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0
particle board and osb	1.4	3.5	5.2	1.4	3.5	4.6	0.0	0.0	0.7
fibreboard	-0.1	0.4	0.6	-0.2	0.5	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.1
Newsprint	0.0	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
Printing & writing	-0.3	0.3	0.2	-0.3	0.3	0.4	0.1	-0.1	-0.2
Packaging	-0.6	1.2	0.7	-0.7	1.7	0.7	0.1	-0.5	0.0
Household & sanitary	-0.1	-0.6	-0.2	-0.1	-0.6	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
Chemical pulp	-0.5	-0.6	0.6	-0.3	0.1	0.1	-0.2	-0.7	0.5
Wood pellets	0.1	0.3	1.0	0.0	0.1	1.4	0.1	0.2	-0.5

Table 3
EU industrial roundwood removals, consumption, and net trade (million m³ over bark).

BaU	Removals			Consumption			Net trade		
	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030
Conif. sawlogs	204.1	208.0	212.7	210.1	213.4	217.5	-6.0	-5.4	-4.8
Non-conif. sawlogs	40.7	41.7	42.9	45.2	45.9	46.8	-4.5	-4.2	-3.9
Conif. pulpwood	120.2	122.4	126.9	110.1	110.5	113.3	10.1	11.9	13.7
Non-conif. pulpwood	58.8	62.7	67.4	95.6	98.1	102.1	-36.9	-35.4	-34.7
Total IRW	423.7	434.8	449.9	461.0	467.9	479.6	-37.3	-33.1	-29.7
Differences between Scenario II and the BaU scenario									
Conif. sawlogs	15.6	24.2	33.9	14.2	23.5	34.5	1.4	0.7	-0.5
Non-conif. sawlogs	-0.5	-0.3	0.9	-0.2	0.4	1.2	-0.2	-0.7	-0.4
Conif. pulpwood	-2.8	-3.0	-1.7	-3.9	-2.4	-2.8	1.1	-0.6	1.1
Non-conif. pulpwood	0.4	1.9	5.7	0.5	3.0	6.3	-0.2	-1.1	-0.6
Total IRW	12.7	22.7	38.8	10.6	24.5	39.2	2.1	-1.7	-0.4
Differences between Scenario III and the BaU scenario									
Conif. sawlogs	0.0	-0.3	-4.8	0.1	-0.2	-4.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.8
Non-conif. sawlogs	0.0	0.0	-1.2	0.0	0.0	-0.9	0.0	0.0	-0.3
Conif. pulpwood	0.2	0.4	-4.5	0.2	0.4	-2.9	0.0	0.0	-1.6
Non-conif. pulpwood	0.1	0.2	-4.6	0.2	0.3	-4.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.6
Total IRW	0.3	0.3	-15.1	0.6	0.6	-11.7	-0.2	-0.3	-3.4
Differences between Scenario IV and the BaU scenario									
Conif. sawlogs	15.7	24.2	33.9	14.6	23.5	34.3	1.4	0.7	-0.5
Non-conif. sawlogs	-0.6	-0.5	0.9	-0.4	0.2	1.2	-0.2	-0.7	-0.4
Conif. pulpwood	-3.4	-3.8	-0.8	-4.6	-3.3	-2.0	1.1	-0.6	1.1
Non-conif. pulpwood	0.3	1.4	6.0	0.3	2.5	6.7	-0.2	-1.1	-0.6
Total IRW	11.9	21.3	39.9	9.9	22.9	40.3	2.1	-1.7	-0.4

Table 4
Production, consumption and net trade of sawnwood (million m³ under bark).

BaU	Production			Consumption			Net trade		
	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030
Austria	9.0	9.3	9.6	6.5	6.7	6.9	2.6	2.6	2.7
Finland	10.9	11.1	11.2	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.7	5.8	5.9
France	6.6	6.7	6.9	10.7	10.8	10.9	-4.1	-4.0	-4.0
Germany	21.1	21.6	22.0	22.1	22.5	23.0	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0
Sweden	18.6	19.0	19.3	6.0	5.9	5.9	12.6	13.0	13.5
UK	3.5	3.5	3.5	9.2	9.2	9.2	-5.8	-5.7	-5.7
Canada	45.4	45.9	46.9	17.5	17.4	17.6	28.0	28.5	29.4
China	35.2	37.3	39.3	45.8	48.4	50.9	-10.6	-11.1	-11.6
Russia	32.2	32.2	32.0	10.7	10.6	10.6	21.5	21.6	21.4
USA	53.1	53.8	52.7	78.9	79.9	78.8	-25.7	-26.1	-26.1
Differences between Scenario II and the BaU scenario									
Austria	0.6	1.2	2.2	0.9	1.5	2.6	-0.2	-0.3	-0.4
Finland	0.5	1.3	1.7	0.8	2.0	3.2	-0.3	-0.7	-1.4
France	0.8	1.0	0.9	1.7	2.9	5.1	-0.8	-1.9	-4.2
Germany	2.1	2.3	2.5	2.2	2.8	3.5	-0.2	-0.4	-1.0
Sweden	0.7	1.2	2.1	1.1	2.3	3.1	-0.4	-1.1	-0.9
UK	0.3	0.6	0.7	1.3	2.6	4.2	-1.0	-2.0	-3.5
Canada	1.4	2.6	4.9	-0.4	-0.8	-1.4	1.8	3.4	6.3
China	-0.2	-0.5	-0.2	-0.5	-1.1	-1.4	0.3	0.6	1.2
Russia	1.1	2.1	3.9	-0.1	-0.3	-0.6	1.2	2.4	4.5
USA	1.0	0.1	-0.6	-1.0	-4.3	-6.9	2.0	4.4	6.3

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Wood-product markets

Solid wood products exhibit stable, albeit modest, production growth over the outlook for the EU as a whole under BaU (Table 2). The EU is a net exporter of all solid wood products except plywood, and net exports increase over the outlook. Paper products—except household & sanitary paper—on the other hand, show declining production over the outlook in BaU, mirroring changes in consumption with very minor changes in net trade. EU chemical pulp production grows at an increasing rate over the projection, while consumption—reflecting the production of paper—stagnates, resulting in gradually decreasing net imports. Wood pellet consumption outgrows production, resulting in gradually increasing net imports over the outlook (Table 2). EU removals and consumption of all IRW assortments grow over the projection in the BaU, while total net

imports gradually decline (Table 3).

Similar to the scenarios of boosting wood construction in EU/EFTA of Eriksson et al. (2012), EU production of coniferous sawnwood in Scenario II does not keep up with consumption increases. As a result, the EU turns from a net exporter to a major net importer over the outlook; by 2030, the increase in imports would account for half of the consumption increase with respect to BaU (Table 2). The same pattern is evident amongst the main producer and/or consumer countries of the EU. In major non-EU producer and consumer countries, production increases while consumption contracts, resulting in increasing net exports or decreasing net imports (Table 4). Hence increased EU consumption displaces consumption in other regions. EU particle board & OSB production more than keeps up with consumption increases, resulting in slightly increased net exports.

In concordance with Johnston and van Kooten (2016) and Jonsson and Rinaldi (2017), our modelling results exhibit competition as well as

Table 5
Production, consumption and net trade of chemical pulp (million metric tons).

BaU	Production			Consumption			Net trade		
	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030	2020	2025	2030
Finland	7.0	7.2	7.5	3.9	3.8	3.9	3.1	3.4	3.6
France	1.0	1.0	1.1	3.3	3.3	3.3	-2.4	-2.3	-2.2
Germany	1.1	1.1	1.1	6.7	6.7	6.7	-5.7	-5.6	-5.6
Portugal	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	3.0	3.1	-3.0	-3.0	-3.1
Spain	1.9	2.0	2.0	1.8	1.9	1.9	0.1	0.1	0.1
Sweden	9.9	10.5	11.4	3.8	3.6	3.4	6.1	6.9	7.9
Brazil	8.9	9.3	9.8	5.1	5.4	5.6	3.8	4.0	4.2
Canada	13.9	15.1	16.7	3.5	3.4	3.3	10.4	11.7	13.4
China	3.0	3.0	3.2	37.9	39.4	40.5	-35.0	-36.4	-37.4
USA	45.4	43.9	41.3	16.7	17.1	17.4	28.7	26.8	24.0
Differences between Scenario III and the BaU scenario									
Finland	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.2
France	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
Germany	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Portugal	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Spain	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Sweden	0.0	0.0	-0.9	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	-1.0
Brazil	0.0	0.0	-0.5	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.0	0.0	-0.2
Canada	0.0	-0.1	-1.6	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.1	-1.7
China	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-1.1	0.1	0.2	1.0
USA	0.0	-0.2	2.7	0.0	-0.1	-0.3	0.0	-0.1	3.0

synergies. For fibreboard, all paper grades except household & sanitary paper, and wood pellets, synergies from increased supply of sawmilling by-products dominate over competition for inputs from increased particle board & OSB production. For chemical pulp, competition effects dominate during the first outlook periods, but by 2030—as a result of the increased amounts of sawmilling by-products—synergies dominate, as production is somewhat higher than under BaU (Table 2), which would benefit EU production of biochemicals and biofuels. EU removals and consumption of coniferous sawlogs increase at roughly the same rate. Removals and consumption of coniferous pulpwood are lower than under BaU (Table 3); a result of significantly increased production and use of “intermediate pulpwood”, i.e., wood chips and particles from coniferous sawnwood production. This latter result mirrors that of Eriksson et al. (2012) for the Swedish forest sector when boosting wood construction.

Modelling outcomes as regards EU production and consumption of

wood-based commodities of scenario III show limited differences—mostly confined to 2030—with respect to BaU. This is a natural consequence of revenues from the chemical pulp byproducts playing a limited role in the overall pulp & paper value chain (Hurmekoski et al., 2018). Thus, after slightly higher production of printing & writing and packaging paper during the first two outlook periods compared with BaU, by 2030 production and consumption of all commodities are lower than under BaU, except for newsprint and packaging paper (higher) and plywood (unchanged). Total EU paper production and consumption are somewhat higher by 2030 than under BaU. Also, production of chemical pulp, after initially marginally higher production, is significantly lower by 2030, while consumption—slightly higher by 2020 and 2025—is only marginally lower than under BaU (Table 2).

Sweden, the largest EU producer and exporter of chemical pulp, is foreseen to experience markedly reduced production and marginally increasing consumption in scenario III—mirroring increased paper

Fig. 2. Harvested wood products (HWP) mitigation potential estimated for 26 EU countries (excluding Malta and Cyprus), expressed as Mt CO₂, from an atmosphere perspective (i.e., negative values denote CO₂ removals), estimated by the present study for the historical period (i.e., until 2015, based on FAOSTAT data) and until 2030, under different scenarios.

production—as compared with BaU by 2030. Consequently, Swedish net exports would decrease significantly relative to the BaU. Major non-EU producers and/or consumers of chemical pulp are foreseen to experience contracting consumption of chemical pulp by 2030 compared with BaU, reflecting lower paper production—displacement from increased EU production. In particular the USA is expected to see significantly increased net exports with respect to BaU, as the modelling outcome also suggests increased production compared to BaU (Table 5).

The modelling outcomes of scenario IV are similar to those of scenario II. However, by 2030, EU chemical pulp production as well as overall EU production and consumption of paper are higher in scenario IV, and the highest of all the four scenarios (Table 2). Hence, apparently a plentiful supply of sawmilling byproducts is essential for the EU pulp & paper industry to benefit fully from lower chemical pulp manufacturing costs resulting from increased demand for pulping byproducts. After initially somewhat lower levels than scenario II, by 2030 EU IRW removals and consumption are the highest of all four scenarios (Table 3), reflecting higher levels of wood products manufacturing. These results re-affirm the central role of the sawnwood industry in the forest-based bioeconomy (see, e.g., Johnston and van Kooten, 2016; Jonsson and Rinaldi, 2017; Hurmekoski et al., 2018), also as regards biochemicals and biofuels.

4.2. EU carbon dynamics

For all scenarios, we estimated a decreasing HWP mitigation potential until 2020, after which increasing IRW demand reverses this trend (see Fig. 2). In scenarios I and III, where the harvest level increases around 12%, the HWP mitigation potential stabilizes around $-23 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, while in scenarios II and IV, with harvest increases of 22% and 27% respectively, the HWP mitigation potential is equal to about $-39 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in 2030.

Apart from the HWP CO_2 removals, the mitigation potential of the forest-based sector also includes the amount of CO_2 directly removed by forests and the possible substitution benefits realized by using wood products instead of other GHG-intensive materials, such as concrete or steel. In scenario I, where no major deviations from current market developments are foreseen (i.e., the BaU scenario), and scenario III, where only the demand for biochemical and biofuels increases, only the mitigation benefit due to the use of fuelwood to substitute for other energy

carriers can be accounted for. In this case, according to our assumptions, in 2030 this benefit is equal to about -72 and $-74 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, for scenario I and III, respectively (see Table 6). Apart from the uncertainty of the SFs assigned to FW, these results do not account for the possible (unknown) material and energy substitution benefits due to the increasing use of biochemicals and biofuels, not accounted for in the present study. SF estimates for biochemicals and biofuels have a very wide range (from negative up to $+40 \text{ tC/tC}$). Hence, though substitution effects from CTO-based diesel and chemicals would be minor—due to the small impacts on chemical pulp production foreseen in the modelling—an increased use of lignin, in abundant potential supply, could have notable effects, either positive or negative, for climate change mitigation.

In scenarios II and IV, an additional mitigation benefit, due to the partial use of IRW to substitute for other energy-intensive materials, can be accounted as the difference between the amount of long-lived (i.e., sawnwood) and medium-lived (i.e., wood-based panels) materials used under the BaU scenario and under scenarios II and IV. The additional mitigation effect, reported on the last column of Table 6, is equal to -28 and $-35 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, for scenario II and IV, respectively. A recent literature review proposed by Leskinen et al. (2018) highlighted the high uncertainty of the SF applied to estimate these values. We can consider these values as a range, representative of the main values proposed by some of the most recent studies, see, e.g., Rüter et al. (2016), Jasinevičius et al. (2017), Nabuurs et al. (2017). As an example, the last mentioned study, using the SF proposed by Sathre and O'Connor (2010), estimated, at EU level, a possible material substitution potential equal to $-43 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in 2050 and, for the same year, an energy substitution potential equal to $-141 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

The forest carbon stock change estimated by CBM for the historical period ranges from about $-416 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in 2000 to about $-322 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in 2015 (see Fig. 3). Under scenario IV, where the future harvest level increases by 27%, this sink declines to about $-146 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in 2030, while under scenarios I and III, where the harvest level increases of about 13%, the final carbon sink is equal to about $-260 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. By adding the carbon sink provided by HWP and the potential emissions saved by material and energy substitution, the total carbon stock change in 2030 is equal to about $-367 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in scenario I, $-312 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in scenario II, $-359 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in scenario III and $-273 \text{ Mt CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in scenario IV.

This means that, considering the HWP mitigation potential, the

Table 6

Material and energy substitution effect estimated, for each scenario, in 2030, by multiplying the potential amount of wood used to substitute for other energy-intensive materials by a substitute factor (SF) assessing the amount of GHG emissions avoided by using wood products instead of other materials. The total amount of roundwood is distinguished between (i) long-lived commodities, including the amount of wood used for sawnwood, (ii) medium-lived commodities, including the amount of wood for the production of wood-based panels, and (iii) fuelwood, used directly for energy production. Within the first scenario, considered BaU, and III, we assume that only the amount of fuelwood removed in 2030 provides a mitigation effect. The additional mitigation potential (M.P., reported on the last column), compared with BaU, is given by the relative difference between scenario I and scenarios II and IV, on the amount of wood used for sawnwood, for wood-based panels, and for fuelwood.

Scenario	Commodity	$\text{m}^3 \cdot 10^3$	Stock in 2030 Substitution effect	Biomass ¹ (t C 10^3)	SF	Overall mitigation effect t C 10^3	Mt CO_2	Additional M.P.
I (BaU)	Long-lived wood	111,062	No subst. effect	1.1	0	0		
	Medium-lived wood	58,387	No subst. effect	0.55	0	0		
	Fuelwood	115,501		25,988	0.76	19,751	-72	
	Substitution effect					19,751	-72	-
II	Long-lived wood	129,300	18,238	4104	1.1	4514	-16	
	Medium-lived wood	63,588	5201	1170	0.55	644	-2	
	Fuelwood	129,704		29,183	0.76	22,179	-81	
	Substitution effect					27,337	-100	-28
III	Long-lived wood	108,648	No subst. effect	1.1	0	0		
	Medium-lived wood	57,328	No subst. effect	0.55	0	0		
	Fuelwood	117,501		26,438	0.76	20,093	-74	
	Substitution effect					20,093	-74	-2
IV	Long-lived wood	129,285	18,223	4100	1.1	4510	-17	
	Medium-lived wood	63,585	5199	1170	0.55	643	-2	
	Fuelwood	140,390		31,588	0.76	24,007	-88	
	Substitution effect					29,160	-107	-35

¹conversion from volume to biomass, using a CF=0.225.

²estimated as absolute difference with BaU.

carbon sink attributed to the forest sector increases from a minimum of 8%, for scenario III, to a maximum of 26%, for scenario IV. Adding material and energy substitution benefits, the forest carbon sink increases from a minimum of 36%, for scenarios I and III, to a maximum of 86%, for scenario IV.

Even so, at least within the relatively short time-frame considered by our study, the maximum carbon sink is provided under BaU (scenario I). Indeed, the carbon sink directly provided by forests in 2030 largely compensates for the absence of any substitution benefits and the lower HWP carbon sink. In line with the main findings proposed by Valade et al. (2017), our results suggest that, within a short time horizon, the additional mitigation potential provided by HWP and substitution is unlikely to compensate for the reduction of the carbon sink directly provided by forest ecosystems. This is also due to the lower apparent half-life coefficients assigned to wood products, compared to the (generally) longer forest cycles, and to the relatively low quantity of wood products providing a substitution effect, compared to the total quantity of wood removed from the forest. Obviously, different assumptions regarding substitution factors and on the final use of wood products (i.e., taking into account the cascade use of wood products,

generally neglected by most studies) may provide different results. However, even assuming higher SFs (e.g., equal to 2.1 kg C kg⁻¹C⁻¹, as suggested by Sathre and O'Connor, 2010), the material substitution benefits would not compensate for the reduction in the forest carbon sink. On the contrary, the average substitution benefits of wood-based products can be assumed to decline in the future, as energy sector emissions decline (e.g., Peñaloza et al., 2018).

More detailed bottom-up approaches, mapping the life cycles of harvested materials and the associated emissions profiles at country level, could improve the estimates of the HWP mitigation potential (Jordan et al., 2018). Within the present study, our projections on the future carbon sink provided by forests are based on a simplified linear regression model that considers neither the evolution of the age class distribution due to the effect of management practices—such as possible improvements applied at local level (Nabuurs et al., 2017)—nor the natural ageing of trees (Pilli et al., 2016b). Further, the effects of climate change, probably negligible within the short time horizon considered by our study, and the increase risk of extreme natural disturbance events, can be essential under a long-term assessment (Valade et al., 2017).

Fig. 3. Net C impact of the forest-based sector, further distinguished between the C stock change, directly estimated by the CBM model for the historical period 2000 – 2015 and derived through the linear regression model until 2030, both reported by the green area (including all forest biomass pools). The additional HWP mitigation potential and material substitution benefits are highlighted by the brown and orange area, respectively. All values are reported in Mt CO₂ yr⁻¹, with negative values highlighting CO₂ removals from the atmosphere. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Employment in millions of hours worked in the EU-26, NACE rev. 2 classification: A02: forestry, C16: manufacture of wood products and products of wood and cork, C17: manufacture of pulp & paper products.

4.3. EU employment

Changes in employment, estimated in working hours, mirror changes in roundwood supply in the forestry sector (A02) and production quantities in wood products (C16) and pulp & paper products (C17) manufacturing sectors. Under BaU (Scenario I), the total number of hours worked increases by 6% from 2015, reaching 4.4 billion hours in 2030 (Fig. 4). Most of this progression takes place in the forestry subsector (+151 million hours or +15% in the sector), while the amount of work in the pulp & paper subsector decreases by 3%.

In scenarios II and IV, total increases in working hours by 2030 with respect to BaU would be 18% and 20% respectively. This results

principally from the manufacture of construction material and its pull effect on the wood supply and thus on the forestry sector. Since the pulp & paper industries benefit from additional availability of industry byproducts, activity and employment in this sector decrease less in these scenarios (-2%) than under BaU. In Scenario III, increased demand for chemical pulp byproducts supports the pulp & paper industries at the beginning of the outlook period, also positively influencing the forestry sector that supplies the raw material. By 2030, the employment in the three sectors analysed will increase less than in the BaU scenario (scenario I).

In this study, changes in employment are estimated for the forest-based sector only, though wood substitution would reasonably affect

How scenarios compare in 2030 with respect to the business-as-usual scenario

Fig. 5. Comparison of scenario results with respect to business-as-usual in 2030 (in percent). Carbon stock change is shown for each component. The final result, given by summing up the contribution of individual components, is reported in red figures. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

employment in other sectors. Further research is needed to evaluate employment implications for the economy as a whole.

4.4. Synthesis

In Fig. 5, scenario outcomes—in terms of harvests, forest-based sector employment, and carbon stock changes in the EU—are compared to the situation in the business-as-usual scenario (scenario I) by 2030. Synergies as well as trade-offs are clearly visible. Thus, the level of activity in the forest-based sector (manufacturing and harvests) and employment show similar trends in all scenarios: higher activity (in the graph, only changes in roundwood harvest levels are shown) entails higher employment. On the other hand, the relation between increased activity and carbon stock change is more complex. Increasing harvests leads to lower carbon stocks in forests, while increased use of solid wood products is beneficial for carbon sequestration in HWP and for substitution of more GHG-intensive materials and energy sources. In the relatively short timeframe considered, the overall effect is one of increased carbon emissions.

Conclusions

This study contributes to the scientific literature dealing with the climate change mitigation implications of wood substitution. Its main scientific contribution rests in the inclusion of new wood-based products in partial equilibrium modelling, which allows the tracking of interactions between different parts of the sector and the resulting cascade impacts in selected scenarios. Hence, widening the scope, we account for international trade in wood products as well as impacts on EU forests and forest-based sector employment of an increased EU uptake of wood-based construction and/or biochemicals and biofuels. To accomplish this, acknowledging and accounting for the intrinsically complex nature of the forest-based sector, we conduct quantitative scenario analysis to assess potential synergies and trade-offs between different uses of forest-based resources, in terms of climate change mitigation approaches, employment and as regards different wood commodities. More specifically, we fully integrate an EU forest resource model with a global wood-product markets model, performing specific analysis of carbon substitution effects and forest-based sector employment.

The modelling outcomes highlight interlinkages in the forest-based sector and clearly indicate the crucial role of wood-based construction in the forest-based bioeconomy. Boosting wood-based construction would thus lead to increased consumption and production of solid wood products while also benefitting other sub-sectors of the forest-based bioeconomy—amongst them biochemicals and biofuels based on chemical pulp byproducts—by generating raw materials for these industries (wood chips, bark, sawdust). These developments would increase EU employment in the forest-based sectors of the bioeconomy. Increased use of wood-based construction at the same time results in drastically increased imports of coniferous sawnwood, turning EU from a net exporter to a large net importer, with carbon flow impacts in other regions.

Within the rather short—in forest resource terms—time frame considered, positive climate change mitigation effects in terms of increased carbon storage in harvested wood products (HWP) and substitution of greenhouse gas-intensive materials is, however, more than offset by reduced net carbon sinks in forests resulting from increased EU roundwood harvests. Further, increased EU imports of coniferous sawnwood results in lower consumption of sawnwood outside the EU, which would reduce extra-EU carbon storage in long-life HWP and substitution of greenhouse gas-intensive materials. Increased harvests of industrial roundwood would exacerbate the situation. However, the analysis of substitution impacts should be further refined in future research to gain a better understanding of this dynamic.

Our results further suggest that—in the current case of biorefineries based on chemical pulp mills—one-sided support of biochemicals and

biofuels and ensuing price increases for pulping byproducts would have very limited effects on wood-based markets (production as well as consumption and net trade), employment in the forest-based sector, and carbon flows. This is a natural consequence of revenues from the chemical pulp byproducts playing a relatively insignificant role in the overall pulp & paper value chain. The supply of these feedstocks for biochemicals and biofuels are thus largely contingent upon the demand for pulp for paper production. The scenario combining increased EU uptake of wood-based construction and a high demand for wood-based biochemicals and biofuels—with the highest EU chemical pulp production as well as overall EU production and consumption of paper by 2030 of all four scenarios—indicates that a plentiful supply of sawmilling byproducts is essential for the pulp & paper, biochemical, and biofuel industries to benefit from an increased demand for pulping byproducts. Biofuels and biochemicals could of course also be produced from other sources of woody biomass, notably sawdust, entailing competition with other uses of these feedstocks, a topic worthy of future research.

The current paper provides an illustration of the complex, interwoven nature of the forest-based sector. Interlinkages and interdependencies between different parts of the sector within a region as well as between different regions make it intrinsically difficult to foresee the reaction to different drivers of change. This calls for complementing qualitative foresight literature with simulation modelling to capture those intricate interlinkages. Thus, the paper contributes to foresight literature on bioeconomy by providing evidence-based decision support for the elaboration of bioeconomy strategies, combining simulation modelling, scenario analysis and impact assessment in an integrated framework. Naturally, the modelling framework requires further efforts, for example, to better capture the demand shifters unrelated to economic activity. Despite its remaining weaknesses, the chosen approach may provide enhanced policy relevance to complement more static scenario analysis and expert opinion-driven analyses.

This study adds to the evidence on potential conflicts, or trade-offs, between, on the one hand, wood substitution and forest carbon sequestration in climate change mitigation efforts in the next few decades, and between job creation on one side and climate change mitigation on the other (cf. Philippidis et al., 2018; Asada et al., 2020). Further, enhanced climate change mitigation in one region might be at odds with efforts to mitigate climate change in other regions. Hence, besides the need for integrated modelling frameworks, our study provides additional testimony to the need for concerted international action in mitigating climate change.

Finally, though the scope of the study is far from disaggregated enough to allow any far-reaching managerial suggestions, our findings confirm, at least to some extent, the benefits of vertical integration in the forest-based industry. There are, in particular, apparent synergies between sawmilling and chemical pulp-based biorefineries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ragnar Jonsson: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Francesca Rinaldi:** Formal analysis, Software, Validation, Writing - original draft. **Roberto Pilli:** Formal analysis, Software, Validation, Writing - original draft. **Giulia Fiorese:** Visualization, Writing - review & editing. **Elias Hurmekoski:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing. **Noemi Cazzaniga:** Data curation. **Nicolas Robert:** Formal analysis. **Andrea Camia:** Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The opinions expressed herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The scientific output does not imply a policy position of the European Commission.

Fig. A.1. The figure reports for each MS and at EU level (on the last plot) the linear relationship ($Y = a + b X$) and the corresponding coefficient of determination (R²) between the total annual removals applied as input by CBM, reported on the x-axis in m³ 10³ yr⁻¹, and the total annual C stock change estimated by model, reported on the y-axis in Gg CO₂ yr⁻¹, including living biomass DOM and soil (negative values highlight a sink). All values refer to the historical period 2000 – 2015.

Fig. A.1. (continued).

Acknowledgements

The work described in this paper—though not constituting its official output—has been carried out in the context of the JRC Biomass assessment study (https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/projects-activities/jrc-biomass-assessment-study_en). Icons in the graphical abstract and in Fig. 5 are from The Noun Project (<https://thenounproject.com/>): log by Sergey Demushkin; worker by Nikita Kozin; tree by AomAm. Dr. Hurmekoski wishes to acknowledge financial support from the Sub-Wood project (No. 321627) funded by the Academy of Finland.

Appendix A. Correlation between C stock change and harvest

The correlation between the total C stock change estimated by CBM (Y) and the total amount of harvest (X), used as input for the historical period 2000–2015, was verified through a simple linear model ($Y = a + bX$), applied both at EU and at country level. The results, summarized in the following figures, highlight that for 21 out of 26 countries, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is > 0.50 , and at EU level $R^2 = 0.86$, with $a = -890,950$ and $b = 1.2035$. Within the present study, the total C stock change at EU level until 2030 was inferred through this last relationship, assuming as independent variable (X) the future amount of harvest as determined for each scenario, excluding any additional effect due to natural disturbances and climate change.

Appendix B. Maximum wood supply (MWS)

For each EU MSs considered, the CBM model estimates the MWS, i.e., the amount of biomass available for the potential supply of roundwood under the same silvicultural practices defined for the historical period, without decreasing the growing stock of the aboveground biomass. Within the present study, basic input data are directly inferred from the MWS reported by Jonsson et al. (2018), updated to 2015 according to the latest CBM runs. The industrial roundwood (IRW) fraction of the MWS (distinguishing between coniferous and non-coniferous) is provided as an input to GFTM, where it is used as an upper bound in the

transformation process as previously outlined. GFTM derives the market equilibrium, including the demand for IRW, which is used to update the growing stocks (coniferous and non-coniferous respectively) and to estimate the next period's harvest potentials.

Appendix C. Substitution Factor (SF)

Consistently with the IPCC approach applied to HWP, we distinguish the total amount of roundwood between: (i) long-lived commodities, including the amount of wood used for sawnwood; (ii) medium-lived commodities, including the amount of wood for the production of wood-based panels; and (iii) fuelwood, directly used for energy production. The SF assigned to each category, inferred by Valade et al. (2017), is equal to $1.1 \text{ kg C kg}^{-1}\text{C}^{-1}$, $0.55 \text{ kg C kg}^{-1}\text{C}^{-1}$ and $0.76 \text{ kg C kg}^{-1}\text{C}^{-1}$, for long-lived, medium-lived and fuelwood, respectively (see Table 6 for further details).

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Dr. Ragnar Jonsson is a scientific project officer at the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC). His-work at JRC concerns the modelling and analysis of wood-based products and energy markets. Ragnar Jonsson holds a PhD in Forest Industry Production systems from Växjö University, a MSc in social sciences from Lund University, and a MSc in forestry from Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences.

Dr. Francesca Rinaldi has a PhD in economics, specializing in decision theory and mathematical finance. In the course of her education as a graduate student, Dr. Rinaldi has developed a strong background in economic theory, while at the same time maintaining a close eye on concrete applications. After five years as a finance researcher, in 2013 Dr. Rinaldi's research focused on the intersection of economic, social and environmental issues, in particular modelling and analysing the socio-economic aspects of the forest sector.

Dr. Pili Roberto is currently employed as scientific project officer at the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, where he provides scientific and technical support regarding forest modelling for the LULUCF sector and the forest biomass assessment. He holds a PhD in Forest Ecology at the University of Padova and a bachelor degree in History at the same university.

Dr. Giulia Fiorese is a researcher at the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC). Her work at JRC contributes to the setting-up of a bio-economy modelling

framework capable of assessing the impacts of different EU policy scenarios with a specific focus on forest biomass and its uses for energy and products. She holds a PhD in Ecology from University of Parma and a master degree in Environmental Engineering from Politecnico di Milano.

Dr. Elias Hurmekoski is a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Helsinki. His expertise and research interests relate primarily to futures studies and foresight methodology, structural changes in forest products markets, and climate change and land use. He has multi-year experience from international and interdisciplinary research organizations and policy support activities. Dr. Hurmekoski holds a PhD in forest economics from the University of Eastern Finland.

Dr. Noemi E. Cazzaniga is an expert in geoinformatics. She is supporting the Bioeconomy Unit of the European Commission Joint Research Centre since 2016. Her current work focuses on forestry data analysis and management and on the development of woody biomass flows for the whole of Europe. She holds a PhD in Geodesy and Geomatics from Politecnico di Milano (Italy) and a Degree in Environmental and Land Planning Engineering from the same University.

Dr. Nicolas Robert is a researcher at the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission. His-research focuses on the supply and use of forest ecosystem services and their contribution to the European economy. He also studies the socio-economic impacts of the forest-based bio-economy. Dr. Robert holds a master's degree in agronomy and PhD in economics from AgroParisTech (France).

Dr. Andrea Camia is senior researcher at the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. He is currently leading the Bioeconomy Project at the JRC Directorate for Sustainable Resources, encompassing the coordination of the JRC Biomass assessment Study and the operation of the European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bio-economy. He holds a PhD in Forest Sciences.